

Financial Revolution, Commercial Banking and Economic Growth: An Analysis of the Nepalese Economy

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Abstract

This paper examines the degree of relationship between the financial revolution, commercial banking and economic growth of Nepal. The motivation for this study therefore, arises from a number of shortcomings, various gaps and unresolved issues in the literature on the linkages between commercial banks and economic growth. It is anticipated that the approach and methods adopted in this research will help to bridge this gap. The main aim of this research is to make a contribution towards the understanding of the relationship between the development of commercial banks and economic growth of Nepal. Granger causality test provides the mixed result. There is the bidirectional causality between per capita real GDP and domestic assets of commercial banks to the total domestic assets. Similarly, there is no causality between per capita real GDP and private sector credit to total credit of commercial banks. Granger causality test also shows the unidirectional causality as per capita real GDP Granger causes private sector credit of commercial banks to GDP but causality in the opposite direction is not supported statistically.

KEYWORDS: Financial Revolution, Commercial banks, Economic Growth and Granger Causality Test.

BACKGROUND

The financial system is a backbone of the economy. It can play vital role in Nepalese economy with mobilizes savings and allocates credit across space and time. It provides not only payment services, but more importantly products which enable firms and households to cope with economic uncertainties by hedging, pooling, sharing, and pricing risks. Banking sector in Nepal is facing a rapidly changing market. Nepalese banking industry has significant changes over past decades as a result of liberalization, deregulation, advances in information technology and globalization. The financial sector

liberalization resulted into entry of new firms in the market; deregulation widened the scope of activities and delimited the banking activities; advancement in technology resulted into new ways and tools to perform banking activities; and globalization added more pressure on competitiveness of individual banks. Nepal has a reasonably diversified financial sector as evidenced by the number and variety of institutions that play an active role in the society. Nepal's financial sector has become deeper, and the number and type of financial intermediation has grown rapidly with in this period. The Nepalese

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financial sector has grown significantly both in terms of business volume and size of assets and market capitalization (Shrestha & Bhandari, 2010).

A well functioning financial sector plays a crucial role in the process of economic development by efficiently mobilizing resources and allocating capital for productive investment projects. Well-organized, efficient, smoothly functioning financial system is an important component of a modern, highly specialized economy. He and Krishnamurthy (2012). After the introduction of financial sector reforms, the number of banks and other financial institutions with variegated types of financial instruments has emerged up. As a first step of initiation to liberalize the financial sector since mid-1980s, entry barriers were removed. Three joint venture banks were established in the three subsequent years from 1985. Following it, interest rates were liberalized gradually. Then, especially after the restoration of democracy in 1990, elected government gave a major thrust on economic and financial liberalization in Nepal. As a result, the number of commercial banks was increasing from 5 in 1990 to 11 in 2000 and 31 commercial banks are working in 2013. The government formulated and implemented various policies for the development of financial sector. Such as, permission to establish private banks, autonomy in the determination of the interest rate, scrapping of statutory liquidity ratio, implementation of the prudential guidelines, removal of credit ceilings, and introduction of open market operations and other indirect instruments of monetary policy. So, now the financial system is significantly improving in quantitative as well as qualitative dimensions in Nepal.

This paper examines the degree of relationship between the development of commercial bank and economic growth in Nepal. The international context of this relationship has long been a subject of interest and with the current financial crisis looming; there is now a re-emergence and a re-evaluation of systematic considerations and principles and practices of decision-making. In other

words, there is a shift from a purely systematic view of the financial system to one primarily concerned with management. This shift provides the author with an opportune moment for investigating and evaluating the relationship between revolution of commercial bank and economic growth from an empirical perspective.

Liberalization of financial system i.e. financial markets and institutions in economy of Nepal allows financial *deepening* which reflects an increasing use of financial intermediation by savers and investors and the monetization of the economy. Another impact of liberalization is allowing efficient *flow* of resources among people and institutions over time. This is most important for economic growth. Efficient financial system encourages savings and reduces constraint on capital accumulation and improves allocation and efficiency of investment by transferring capital from less productive to more productive sectors and or regions. More recent research, however, indicates that the commercial banks play a critical role in the economy. Various studies support the commercial bank is a positive impact on economic growth (e.g. King & Levine 1993a; Levine et al., 2000; Rousseau & Wachtel, 2000; and Jalil and Ma, 2008).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Financial institution is an important activity in the economy. They perform a wide variety of functions in financial system. Through their role of allocating capital, monitoring managers, mobilizing savings and promoting technological changes among others, financial intermediaries play a significant role in economic growth. Finance has for a long time been a neglected area in development literature, but a number of recent writings have helped to redress this imbalance. This neglect of finance as regards economic development is somewhat surprising, considering key role that savings and investments play in the theory of economic growth as described by Harrod (1939), Domar (1946), Solow (1956) and the importance ascribed to it by Schumpeter

(1911) in his theory of economic development, McKinnon (1973) and Shaw (1973) and proponents of their views. Banks and financial intermediations bridge the maturity mismatch between savers and investors. They facilitate payments between economic parties by providing a payment, settlement and clearing system. Therefore, they involve to transfers qualitative asset between savers and investors. To provide qualitative services as well as safety for the savers and investors, the sustainability of financial intermediation, there is required effective regulation. The regulations also play vital roles for the intermediaries and banks to enact in the production of their financial services.

Role of Financial Institutions in Economic Growth

The financial revolution is required for every nation and increasingly its roles every period of time. Financial institutions and banking system may make a positive contribution to economic growth; this effect may be counteracted by other factors in the economy. Financial development occurs when financial instruments, markets and intermediaries ameliorate though not necessarily eliminate the effects of information, enforcement and transaction costs, and therefore better provide financial services. Thus, financial development involves improvements in the (i) production of ex-ante information about possible investments, (ii) monitoring of investments and implementation of corporate governance, (iii) trading, diversification, and management of risks, (iv) mobilization and pooling of savings, and (v) exchange of goods and services. Each of these financial functions/services may influence saving and investment decisions and hence economic growth. Since many market frictions exist, and laws, regulations and policies differ remarkably across economies and over time, the impact of financial development on growth may have different implications for resource allocation and welfare in the economy.

Joseph Shumpeter (1911) believed that there were closed relationship between financial institutions and economic development. According to him, the banks and financial institutions were needed for the technological innovation. The technological innovation is one of the most important factors of economic development. Among the various services associated with financial intermediaries, one may refer mobilizing savings, evaluating projects, managing risk, monitoring managers, and facilitating transactions. Many are the authors who, almost ninety years after Shumpeter, in recent studies on economic growth, pay a particular attention to the links between financial systems and the pace of economic development. Schumpeter's view was later formalised by Goldsmith (1969); McKinnon (1973); Shaw (1973); King and Levine (1993 a,b); Fry (1995) and Pagano (1993), to name just a few, who all believed that financial development is a catalyst for economic growth.

Although plausible, the importance and correlation between financial sector development and economic growth is not the only possible description of reality, since growth can also be good for finance. Indeed, many well-known scholars, including Robinson (1952) and Ireland (1994), have long rejected this hypothesis on purely theoretical grounds. In their view, a lack of financial development is simply the manifestation of a lack of and for financial services. As the real sector of the economy expands, the various financial services increases, and will thus be met by the financial sector. Robinson (1952) argued that financial development follows growth, and articulated this causality argument by suggesting that "where enterprise leads finance follows". Even though conclusions must be drawn with caution, the preponderance of theoretical reasoning and empirical evidence suggests a positive, first-order relationship between financial development and economic growth (i.e. finance is related with and leads to economic growth).

If these opposing theories are a correct representation of reality, then policy efforts to promote financial development will be premature, and will in fact amount to a waste of scarce resources. However, if the opposite theory is not correct, policy-makers should focus attention on the creation and promotion of modern financial institutions, including banks, non-banks and stock markets, in order to promote genuine and enduring economic growth.

King and Levine (1993a) build an endogenous growth model, taking into consideration the Schumpeterian idea that financial institutions are important because they evaluate and finance entrepreneurs in their initiation of innovative activity and the bringing of new products to market. They conclude that better financial systems improve the probability of successful innovation and thereby accelerate economic growth. In their empirical work (King and Levine, 1993b, Maxwell Fry, 1997), real per capita GDP growth is found to be strongly associated with various measures of the level of financial development (such as the ratio of liquid liabilities to GDP and the ratio of commercial bank paper to central bank credit), as well as the rate of physical capital accumulation, and improvements in the efficiency with which economies employ physical capital.

Greenwood and Jovanovic (1990) and Bencivenga and Smith (1992) have given a new impetus to the relationship between financial development and growth as these models postulate that savings behavior directly influences not only equilibrium income levels but also growth rates. Thus, financial markets can have a strong impact on real economic activity. On the other hand, Luintel and Khan (1999) have used endogenous growth models to show a two-way relationship between financial development and economic growth. However, despite the emergence of new growth theories, the debate on the direction of causality between financial development and economic growth remains apparent yet. Greenwood and Jovanovic (1990) have addressed the context of financial structure and economic development

to show causal relationship between financial development and economic growth in Pareto-optimal competitive model. Economic growth provides the development of financial structure and, in turn, allows for higher growth through efficiency in investment. Assuming that many entrepreneurs solicit capital and that capital is scarce, financial intermediaries produce better information on firms, thereby fund firms to more promising and induce a more efficient allocation of capital.

King and Levine (1993a, 1993b) have found that besides identifying the best production technologies, financial intermediaries may also boost the rate of technological innovation by identifying those entrepreneurs with the best chances of successfully initiating new goods and production processes. King and Levine (1993a) have examined the capital accumulation and productivity growth channels of 77 countries over the period 1960-1989, by systematically controlling for other factors affecting long-run growth, they construct additional measures of the level of financial development, and analyze whether the level of financial development predicts long-run economic growth, capital accumulation, and productivity growth. They found very consistent results across the different financial development indicators. They however, simply found the potentially large long-term growth effects from changes in financial development.

Levine (1997) has assessed theoretical and empirical evidences on finance growth nexus that the financial system that active role in the economic growth. Development of financial institutions and markets are crucial for the long run growth process. The development in the non-financial (i.e. real) sector, information and technological changes, innovations of computer, financial and monetary and other economic policy, legal and political system and institutions etc have a direct influence in the development of the financial system

Further, Levine (2004) has suggested that the countries with better functioning financial system

(whether bank-based or market-based), grow faster and it eases constraints on external finance. He has stressed on co-evolution of finance and growth. Technological innovation may foster growth in the presence of a well functioning financial system. It also affects the operation of financial systems by transforming the acquisition, processing, and dissemination of information. Importantly, the financial system may provide different services at different stages of economic development, so that the financial system promotes growth.

Calderon and Liu (2003) have examined pooled data of 109 countries to examine the direction of causality between financial development and economic growth by employing Geweke Decomposition test. They found the five distinct results as; financial development generally leads economic growth; bi-directional causality between financial development and economic growth; in developing countries, financial deepening causes more to growth than industrial countries (supply leading supportive); financial development has larger effect on economic growth in long run; financial deepening contributes economic growth through more rapid capital accumulation and productivity growth.

Jalil and Ma (2008) studied that the impact on the financial development and economic growth in China and Pakistan. Their hypothesis were "financial development leads to growth" under the ARDL framework by using the deposit liability ratio and credit to private sector as the indicators of financial development. They found that a positive and significant relationship between financial development and economic growth exists in the case of Pakistan. But, in the case of China, their analysis showed that a positive and significant relationship for credit liability ratio and a positive, yet insignificant, relationship with credit to private sector.

Demetriades and Luintel (1996) have examined the effects of banking sector policies on the process

of financial development and economic growth of Nepal over the period of 1960-1992 by using unrestricted error correction model (UECM). The dynamics between financial development and economic growth are examined by exogeneity tests. They have also constructed the index of financial repression by using principal component method to quantify the influences of banking sector policies on financial development, independently of the interest rate. They could not find support for real interest rate as determinant of financial development. They have jointly determined financial development and economic growth. In other words, policies determining financial depth also influence economic growth and vice-versa.

Recent publications by Bhetuwal (2007) and Poudel (2005) found that financial development (FD) contributes positively to domestic economic growth. On the other hand, Shrestha (2005) did not find any significant relationship between economic growth and financial development. A recent study by Nepal Rastra Bank suggests that domestic economic growth is found to be somewhat supported by financial development; but the effect is noticeable with a one-year lag, but not at a contemporaneous level (NRB, 2009). In this context of mixed results, the appropriate development of Nepalese financial sector is essential so that it can play a critical and positive role in the economic growth of the nation.

METHODOLOGY

Unit Root Test

The Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test is the most popular methods of identification of stationary or non stationary variables. These tests were undertaken under the assumption of the existence of a unit root (H_0) and a stationary variable in the alternative hypothesis (H_a). If the calculated statistics is greater than McKinnon's critical value, then the H_0 or that the variable is not stationary, is not rejected. If the variables are not stationary, these are transferred from non-stationary to stationary by difference methods.

According to the Dickey-Fuller (DF) model is as follows:

$$y_t = m + a\Delta y_{t-1} + e_t \quad (1)$$

Where m is an intercept and e_t is a white noise. According to this model, the null hypothesis is $m = 1$ (non-stationary series) against the alternative hypothesis of $a < 1$ (stationary series). The error term in DF test might be serially correlated. The possibility of such serial correlation is eliminated in the following

Augmented Dickey-Fuller model:

$$\Delta y_t = \mu + \delta y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i \Delta y_{t-i} + e_t \quad [2]$$

Where, $d = a - 1$

The null hypothesis of ADF is $d = 0$ against the alternative hypothesis of $d < 0$. Non-rejection of the null hypothesis implies that the time series is non-stationary whereas rejection means the time series is stationary. Phillips and Perron (PP) have suggested a nonparametric test as an alternative to the ADF test. Although the ADF test has been reported to be more reliable than the PP test, the problem of size distortion and low power of test make both these tests less useful (Maddala and Kim, 2003).

Co-integration Test

The tests of stationarity as explained above validate that the non-stationarity problem of most of the macroeconomic and financial time series variables of level form data results spurious relation but most of the first difference data are free from this drawbacks. The conclusions derived from differenced data may mislead the long-run relationship between the variables (Engle and Granger, 1987). Relationship between the variables computed under differenced data in different orders show short-term relationship which can be considered as disequilibrium relationship. The long-run relationship can be established by using level form data only when variables are co-integrated in same order however,

their linear relationship must be less than the co-integrating order. Now, μ_t is subjected to unit root analysis and it is found to be stationary; that is, it is $I(0)$. This is an interesting situation, for although two variables are individually $I(1)$, that is, they have stochastic trends, their linear combination of them is $I(0)$. So to speak, the linear combination cancels out the stochastic trends in the two series. As a result, a regression would be meaningful (i.e., not spurious). In this case, it is said that the two variables are co-integrated. Economically speaking, two variables will be co-integrated if they have a long-term, or equilibrium relationship between them.

Granger Causality Test

In order to examine whether one variable is causally related to another, Granger (1969) introduced a concept of causality which is commonly known as, 'Granger Causality'. Prior to 1990, the most widely used concept of causality was Granger's notion of causality for temporal systems. Financial development (FD) does not Granger causes economic growth (GDP) when inclusion of the history of F cannot help reduce the prediction error of next period's GDP. Granger causality implies predictability and exogeneity. If the time-series under investigation are not stationary, the first differences are calculated and Granger causality tests proceed as before. This method is inaccurate in that it eliminates the long-term relationship between the variables under consideration. The concept is based on the idea that the future cannot affect the present or the past.

Testing only for long-run causal relationship between commercial banks' development and economic growth would lead to wrong conclusion. Because most of the benefits of higher level of commercial banks' development could be realized in the short-run and the effects may disappear slowly in the long-run, it is important to distinguish the long- and short-run causality. According to the Engle and Granger (1987) representation theorem, if two variables are co-integrated and

each is individually $I(1)$, that is, integrated of order 1 (i.e., each is individually non-stationary), then first variable may Granger-cause second variable, second variable may Granger-cause first variable or each other.

On the above background, it is first necessary to find out whether the two variables are individually non-stationary or co-integrated of $I(1)$. If the variables are not co-integrated, then the whole question of causality may become moot (Gujarati, 2004). More about co-integration has explained below. The testing procedure involves three steps: First, examining the existence of unit roots of macroeconomic and commercial banks' development variables by using Augmented Dickey- Fuller (ADF) test. Second, co-integration test for of the same variables by Johansen co-integration test procedure. If co-integration is detected, the third step is to test for causality by employing the Granger Causality Test.

The study used the natural logarithms of following variables.

Dependent Variable: Real GDP per capita is used as the proxy of economic growth. Real GDP is measured at basic price of a particular year and real GDP per capita is calculated by dividing the real GDP by total population of the country in a particular year.

Independent Variables: Following variables are used as the proxy for development of commercial banks:

1. Ratio of domestic assets of commercial banks to the sum of domestic assets of Nepal Rastra Bank and commercial banks (C/D): It is one of major indicators to measure the development of commercial banks. This ratio measures the size of commercial banks as the financial intermediaries.
2. Ratio of private sector credit to total loans and advances of commercial banks (PC/TL): The ratio of commercial banks' credit to private sector to total loans and advances (PC/TL) is used to measure the

availability of total assets of commercial banks' in the economy. Because banking system extends credit to the private sector as well as government and public enterprises simultaneously. It gauges to what extent the credit is available to the private sector out of total assets of the commercial banks.

3. Ratio of credit to private sector to GDP (PC/GDP): It is the ratio of total credit available to the private sector by commercial banks to nominal GDP. It depicts the size of private sector credit in terms of the size of the economy.

Out of three independent variables C/D measures the size of commercial banks as the financial intermediaries. PC/TL and PC/GDP measure to whom the commercial banks allocates the resources.

The relation is expressed in the multiple regression form as:

$$L(GDP) = \beta_1 + \beta_2 L(C/D) + \beta_3 L(PC/TL) + \beta_4 L(PC/GDP) + \varepsilon_t$$

Where,

$L(GDP)$ = natural logarithm of per capita real GDP

$L(C/D)$ = natural logarithm of ratio of domestic assets of commercial banks to the total domestic assets

$L(PC/TL)$ = natural logarithm of the ratio of commercial banks' credit to private sector to total loans and advances

$L(PC/GDP)$ = natural logarithm of the ratio of total credit available to the private sector by commercial banks to nominal GDP

β_1 = constant term; β_2 = regression coefficient with regard to $L(C/D)$

β_3 = regression coefficient with regard to $L(PC/TL)$;

β_4 = regression coefficient with regard to $L(PC/GDP)$;

ε_t = error term.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For the research purpose, among different financial institutions of Nepal; commercial banks are chosen. There are altogether 31 commercial banks in the country so far. The research has considered the last 38 years data (from 1975 to 2012) for the development of commercial banks and the economic growth of the country.

Unit Root Test in First Difference

The null hypothesis of non-stationarity in log of GDP, log of C/D, log of PC/TL and log of PC/GDP cannot be rejected in level test. Most of the time series data are expected to be found first difference stationary. In order to confirm the validity of the argument, ADF test statistics have been derived from the first difference. In order to test the first difference in time series data, the null hypothesis of unit root problem in first difference in time series data is equal to zero, that is, there is unit root problem in first difference against the alternative hypothesis of zero, i.e., there is no unit root problem in such data.

Testing of non-stationarity from ADF test is to take the first difference including no intercept in test equation with lagged difference one. The adjusted sample included the data from 1975 to 2012 after adjusting endpoints i.e.37 observations. The result of this test is summarized in the table below.

Table 1: Unit root test in first difference

Variables	ADF test statistic
L (GDP)	-4.5571
L (C/D)	-4.8136
L(PC/TL)	-4.1241
L(PC/GDP)	-4.3542

Where,

L (GDP) = natural logarithm of per capita real GDP

L (C/D) = natural logarithm of ratio of domestic assets of commercial banks to the total domestic assets

L (PC/TL) = natural logarithm of the ratio of commercial banks' credit to private sector to total loans and advances

L (PC/GDP) = natural logarithm of the ratio of total credit available to the private sector by commercial banks to nominal GDP

The computed values of ADF statistic for L (GDP) is -4.5571 which is greater than the absolute MacKinnon critical value at all the level of significance under consideration. Likewise, the computed values of ADF statistic for L (C/D), L (PC/TL), and L (PC/GDP) are -4.8136, -4.1241, and -4.3542 respectively. However the MacKinnon critical values at 1percent, 5 percent and 10 percent level of significance are -3.6353, -2.9499, and -2.6133 respectively. Comparing these values in there absolute form, the computed values of ADF statistic of all the variables are greater than the MacKinnon critical values at 1 percent, 5 percent and 10 percent level of significance. This implies that the null hypothesis of non-stationarity in log of GDP, log of C/D, log of PC/TL and log of PC/GDP are rejected in first difference.

In summing up, all the variables which are not stationary in level form data are shown stationary in their first difference. The ADF statistics of all the four variables in their absolute form are greater than MacKinnon critical value at 1 percent, 5 percent and 10 percent level of significance. Therefore, the first difference data are stationary or they are integrated of order 1 or I (1).

Co-integration Test

In order to derive the stable long-run relationship between economic growth and development of commercial bank explanatory variables of Nepal, the Johansen co-integration tests have been performed to validate the variables whether they are co-integrated in same order. The test assumption is the linear deterministic trend in the data.

Co-integration Test between L(GDP) and L(C/D)

The Johansen co-integration test has been performed in the series L(GDP) and L(C/D). The included number of observation in between 1975 to 2012 is 36. Furthermore, the test allowed for the linear deterministic trend in the data and there is no trend assumed in the co-integrating equation and test VAR. The assumed lag interval (pairs) in VAR is 1 to 1. The test results are presented in table below:

Table 2 (A): Co-integration test between L(GDP) & L(C/D)

Lags interval: 1 to 1

Eigen value	Likelihood ratio	5 % critical value	1 % critical value	Hypothesized no. of CE(s)
0.3265	15.3978	15.41	20.04	None
0.0440	1.6112	3.76	6.65	At most 1

*(**) denotes rejection of the 5% (1%) significance level

L.R. rejects any co-integration at 5% significance level

The values of likelihood ratio between these two variables are 15.3978 and 1.6112 considering 'no hypothesized co-integrating equations' and 'at most one co-integrating equation'. However, critical values for 1 percent and 5 percent level of significance in the first case are 20.04 and 15.41 respectively and that of second case are 6.65 and 3.76 respectively. As the likelihood ratio in both the cases is less than the critical value, there is no co-integration presence at 1 percent and 5 percent level of significance.

Similarly, test has been performed in the series L(GDP) and L(C/D) assuming 1 to 2 lag interval (pairs) in vector auto regression variables (VAR). The included number of observation in between 1975 to 2012 is 35. The test results are given in the following Table:

Table 2 (B): Co-integration test between L(GDP) & L(C/D)

Lags interval: 1 to 2

Eigen value	Likelihood ratio	5 % critical value	1 % critical value	Hypothesized no. of CE(s)
0.470431	22.1342	15.41	20.04	None **
0.012529	0.4316	3.76	6.65	At most 1

*(**) denotes rejection of the 5% (1%) significance level

L.R. test indicates 1 co-integrating equation(s) at 5% significance level

Normalized co-integrating coefficients: 1 co-integrating equation(s)

L(GDP)	L(C/D)	C
1.000000	-1.6798 (0.13398)	-9.9880
Log likelihood		148.4210

The values of likelihood ratio between these two variables are 22.1342 and 0.4316 considering 'no hypothesized co-integrating equations' and 'at most one co-integrating equation'. However, critical values for 1 percent and 5 percent level of significance in the first case are 20.04 and 15.41 respectively and that of second case are 6.65 and 3.76 respectively. As the likelihood ratio the first case is greater than the critical value, there is the presence of one co-integrating equation at 1 percent and 5 percent level of significance. Furthermore, the co-integrating equation between Log of GDP and Log of C/D with normalized co-integrating coefficients has also shown in the above table. The presence of co-integrating equation indicates that there exists the long run relationship between L(GDP) and L(C/D).

Co-integration Test between L(GDP) and L(PC/TL)

The Johansen co-integration test has been performed in the series L(GDP) & L(PC/TL). The test allowed

for the linear deterministic trend in the data and there is no trend assumed in co-integrating equation and test VAR. Furthermore, the assumed lag interval (pairs) in vector auto regression variables (VAR) is 1 to 1. The included number of observation in between 1975 to 2012 is 36. The test results are given in the table below:

Table 3(A): Co-integration test between L(GDP) & L(PC/TL)

Lags interval: 1 to 1

Eigen value	Likelihood ratio	5 % critical value	1 % critical value	Hypothesized no. of CE(s)
0.212681	8.910216	15.41	20.04	None
0.015337	0.540952	3.76	6.65	At most 1

*(**) denotes rejection of the 5% (1%) significance level

L.R. rejects any co-integration at 5% significance level

The values of likelihood ratio between these two variables are 8.9211 and 0.5510 considering 'no hypothesized co-integrating equations' and 'at most one co-integrating equation'. However, critical values for 1 percent and 5 percent level of significance in the first case are 20.04 and 15.41 respectively and that of second case are 6.65 and 3.76 respectively. As the likelihood ratio in both the cases is less than the critical value, there is no co-integration presence at 1 percent and 5 percent level of significance. Similarly, test has been performed in the series L(GDP) and L(PC/TL) assuming 1 to 2 lag interval (pairs) in vector auto regression variables (VAR). The included number of observation in between 1975 to 2012 is 35. The test results are given in the following Table:

Table 3 (B): Co-integration test between L(GDP) & L(PC/TL)

Lags interval: 1 to 2

Eigen value	Likelihood ratio	5 % critical value	1 % critical value	Hypothesized no. of CE(s)
0.2030	8.7162	15.41	20.04	None
0.02619	0.9049	3.76	6.65	At most 1

The values of likelihood ratio between these two variables are 8.7162 and 0.9049 considering 'no hypothesized co-integrating equations' and 'at most one co-integrating equation'. However, critical values for 1 percent and 5 percent level of significance in the first case are 20.04 and 15.41 respectively and that of second case are 6.65 and 3.76 respectively. As the likelihood ratio in both the cases is less than the critical value, there is no co-integration presence at 1 percent and 5 percent level of significance.

Co-integration Test between L(GDP) and L(PC/GDP)

The Johansen co-integration test has been performed in the series L(GDP) and L(PC/GDP). The test allowed for the linear deterministic trend in the data and there is no trend assumed in co-integrating equation and test VAR. Furthermore, the assumed lag interval (pairs) in vector auto regression variables (VAR) is 1 to 1. The included number of observation in between 1975 to 2012 is 36. The test results are given in the following Table:

Table 4(A): Co-integration test between L(GDP) & L(PC/GDP)

Lags interval: 1 to 1

Eigen value	Likelihood ratio	5 % critical value	1 % critical value	Hypothesized no. of CE(s)
0.4105	19.5106	15.41	20.04	None *
0.03101	1.1008	3.76	6.65	At most 1

*(**) denotes rejection of the 5% (1%) significance level

L.R. test indicates 1 co-integrating equation(s) at 5% significance level

Normalized co-integrating coefficients: 1 co-integrating equation(s)

LOG (PRGDP)	L(PC/GDP)	G
1.000000	-0.3884 (0.02542)	-10.4135
Log likelihood		120.7601

The values of likelihood ratio between these two variables are 19.5106 and 1.1008 considering 'no hypothesized co-integrating equations' and 'at most one co-integrating equation'. However, critical values for 1 percent and 5 percent level of significance in the first case are 20.04 and 15.41 respectively and that of second case are 6.65 and 3.76 respectively. As the likelihood ratio the first case is greater than the critical value, there is the presence of one co-integrating equation at 5 percent level of significance. Furthermore, the co-integrating equation between Log of GDP and L(PC/GDP) with normalized co-integrating coefficients has also shown in the above table. The presence of co-integrating equation indicates that there exists the long run relationship between L(GDP) and L(PC/GDP).

Similarly, test has been performed in the series L(GDP) and L(PC/GDP) assuming 1 to 2 lag interval (pairs) in vector auto regression variables (VAR). The included number of observation in between 1975 to 2012 is 35. The test results are given in the following Table:

Table 4 (B): Co-integration test between L(GDP) & L(PC/GDP)

Lags interval: 1 to 2

Eigen value	Likelihood ratio	5% critical value	1% critical value	Hypothesized no. of CE(s)
0.2963	13.1017	15.41	20.04	None
0.03252	1.1242	3.76	6.65	At most 1

*(**) denotes rejection of the 5% (1%) significance level

L.R. rejects any co-integration at 5% significance level

The values of likelihood ratio between these two variables are 13.1017 and 1.1242 considering 'no hypothesized co-integrating equations' and 'at most one co-integrating equation'. However, critical values for 1 percent and 5 percent level of significance in the first case are 20.04 and 15.41 respectively and that of second case are 6.65 and 3.76 respectively. As the likelihood ratio in both the cases is less than the critical value, there is no co-integration presence at 1 percent and 5 percent level of significance.

The Johansen co-integration test indicated that there exists one co-integrating equation between log of real GDP per capita and log of commercial bank assets to total domestic assets at 1 percent and 5 percent level of significance. Similarly, one co-integrating relationship is confirmed in between log of per capita GDP and log of total credit available to the private sector through commercial banks to GDP at 5 percent level of significance. The existence of co-integration implies that there is long-run relationship between those variables during the review period. However, no co-integrating relationship is found between log of real GDP per capita and log of commercial banks' credit to private sector to total credit.

Granger Causality Test

From the above Johansen co-integration test, it has been found that there exists the long term relationship between log of real GDP per capita and log of commercial bank assets to total domestic assets at 1 percent and 5 percent level of significance. Similarly, the long term is relationship is also confirmed in between log of per capita GDP and log of total credit available to the private sector through commercial banks to GDP at 5 percent level of significance. According to the Engle and Granger (1987) representation theorem, if two variables are co-integrated and each is individually I (1), that is,

integrated of order 1 (i.e., each is individually non-stationary), then first variable may Granger-cause second variable, second variable may Granger-cause first variable or each other. Granger causality test has been performed as follows:

Granger Causality Test between L(GDP) & L(C/D)

Table 5: Granger causality test between L(GDP) & L(C/D)

Null hypothesis	Obs	Lags	F-statistic	Prob
L(GDP) does not Granger cause L(C/D) L(C/D) does not Granger cause L(GDP)	37	1	5.5011 4.4091	0.0263 0.0425
L(GDP) does not Granger cause L(C/D) L(C/D) does not Granger cause L(GDP)	36	2	3.1576 3.6112	0.0604 0.0422
L(GDP) does not Granger cause L(C/D) L(C/D) does not Granger cause L(GDP)	35	3	5.4114 3.9103	0.0049 0.0208
L(GDP) does not Granger cause L(C/D) L(C/D) does not Granger cause L(GDP)	34	4	4.1120 2.2260	0.0112 0.0964

Granger causality test has been performed between L(GDP) and L(C/D) considering the different lag length. In case of null hypothesis 'L(GDP) does not Granger cause L(C/D)' the F-statistics are 5.5011, 3.1576, 5.4114 and 4.1120 for the lag length 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively. In the meantime, the values of probability for the lag length 1, 2, 3 and 4 are 0.0263, 0.0604, 0.0049, and 0.0112 respectively. The above table shows that values the F-statistics is significant at 2.63 percent level of significance for the lag length 1. In case of lag length 2, it is

significant at 6.04 percent level of significance. When lag length is considered as 3, F-statistics is significant at 0.49 percent level of significance. Similarly, in case of lag length 4, it is significant at 1.12 percent level of significance. That means the null hypothesis 'L(GDP) does not Granger cause L(C/D)' has been rejected at 5 percent level of significance considering the lag length 1, 3 and 4 whereas for the lag length 2, it has been rejected at 6 percent level of significance.

Similarly, In case of null hypothesis 'L(C/D) does not Granger Cause L(GDP)' the F-statistics are 4.4091, 3.6112, 3.9103, and 2.2260 for the lag length 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively. Similarly, the values of probability for the lag length 1, 2, 3 and 4 are 0.0425, 0.0422, 0.0208, and 0.0964 respectively.

Analyzing the value of F-statistics and probability, it can be concluded that the F-statistics is significant at 4.25 percent level of significance for the lag length 1. In case of lag length 2, it is significant at 4.22 percent level of significance. When lag length is considered as 3, F-statistics is significant at 2.08 percent level of significance. However, in case of lag length 4, it is significant at 9.64 percent level of significance. That means the null hypothesis 'L(C/D) does not Granger Cause L(GDP)' has been rejected at 5 percent level of significance considering the lag length 1, 2 and 3 whereas for the lag length 4, it has been rejected at 10 percent level of significance.

From the above analysis it can be concluded that there is bidirectional causality between log of per capita real GDP [L(GDP)] and log of domestic assets of commercial banks to the total domestic assets [L(C/D)]. That means L(C/D) Granger causes L(GDP) and L(GDP) Granger causes L(C/D).

Granger Causality Test between L(GDP) & L(PC/TL)

Table 6: Granger causality test between L(GDP) & L(PC/TL)

Null hypothesis	Obs	Lags	F-statistic	Prob
L(GDP) does not Granger cause L(PC/TL) L(PC/TL) does not Granger cause L(GDP)	37	1	1.9139 0.4011	0.1830 0.5449
L(GDP) does not Granger cause L(PC/TL) L(PC/TL) does not Granger cause L(GDP)	36	2	2.9012 0.1812	0.07416 0.840
L(GDP) does not Granger Cause L(PC/TL) L(PC/TL) does not Granger Cause L(GDP)	35	3	2.2014 0.3910	0.1141 0.7510
L(GDP) does not Granger cause L(PC/TL) L(PC/TL) does not Granger cause L(GDP)	34	4	1.4201 0.0351	0.2588 0.9981

Although there is no co-integrating relationship between L(GDP) and L(PC/TL), Granger causality test has been performed between them considering the different lag length. In case of null hypothesis 'L(GDP) does not Granger Cause L(PC/TL)' the F-statistics are 1.9139, 2.9012, 2.2014, and 1.4201 for the lag length 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively. In the meantime, the values of probability for the lag length 1, 2, 3 and 4 are 0.1830, 0.07416, 0.1141, and 0.2588 respectively. The above table shows that the values of F-statistics are insignificant at 5 percent level of significance for all the lag lengths under consideration. Only in the case of lag length 2, it is significant at 7.4 percent level of significance. That means the null hypothesis 'L(GDP) does not Granger Cause L(PC/TL)' can't be rejected at 5 percent level of significance.

Similarly, in case of null hypothesis 'L(PC/TL) does not Granger Cause L(GDP)' the F-statistics are 0.4011, 0.1812, 0.3910, and 0.0351 for the lag length 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively. Also, the values of probability for the lag length 1, 2, 3 and 4 are 0.5449, 0.840, 0.7510, and 0.9981 respectively. Analyzing the value of F-statistics and probability, it can be concluded that the F-statistics are insignificant at 5 percent level of significance for all the lag length under consideration. That means the null hypothesis 'L(PC/TL) does not Granger Cause L(GDP)' can't be rejected at 5 percent level of significance.

From the above analysis it can be concluded that there is no causality between log of per capita real GDP [L(GDP)] and log of private sector credit to total credit of commercial banks [L(PC/TL)]. That means L(GDP) does not Granger cause L(PC/TL) and L(PC/TL) does not Granger cause L(GDP).

Granger Causality Test between L(GDP) & L(PC/GDP)

Table 6: Granger causality test between L(GDP) & L(PC/GDP)

Null hypothesis	Obs	Lags	F-statistic	Prob
L(GDP) does not Granger cause L(PC/GDP) L(PC/GDP) does not Granger cause L(GDP)	37	1	4.8213 2.5213	0.0361 0.1210
L(GDP) does not Granger cause L(PC/GDP) L(PC/GDP) does not Granger cause L(GDP)	36	2	8.2011 1.0801	0.00162 0.3524
L(GDP) does not Granger cause L(PC/GDP) L(PC/GDP) does not Granger cause L(GDP)	35	3	4.0721 0.4012	0.0171 0.7601
L(GDP) does not Granger cause L(PC/GDP) L(PC/GDP) does not Granger cause L(GDP)	34	4	3.8810 0.6715	0.0145 0.6206

Granger causality test has also been performed between L(GDP) and L(PC/GDP). In case of null hypothesis 'L(GDP) does not Granger cause L(PC/GDP)' the F-statistics are 4.8213, 8.2011, 4.0721 and 3.8810 for the lag length 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively. Similarly, the values of probability for the lag length 1, 2, 3 and 4 are 0.0361, 0.00162, 0.0171, and 0.0145 respectively. The above table shows that values the F-statistics are significant at 3.61 percent level of significance for the lag length 1. In case of lag length 2, it is significant at 0.162 percent level of significance. For the lag length 3, F-statistics is significant at 1.71 percent level of significance. Similarly, in case of lag length 4, it is significant at 1.45 percent level of significance. That means the null hypothesis 'L(GDP) does not Granger cause L(PC/GDP)' has been rejected at 5 percent level of significance for all the lag length under consideration.

Similarly, in case of null hypothesis 'L(PC/GDP) does not Granger Cause L(GDP)' the F-statistics are 2.5213, 1.0801, 0.4012, and 0.6715 for the lag length 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively. Meanwhile, the values of probability for the lag length 1, 2, 3 and 4 are 0.1210, 0.3524, 0.7601, and 0.6206 respectively. Analyzing the value of F-statistics and probability, it can be concluded that the F-statistics are insignificant at 5 percent level of significance for all the lag length under consideration. That means the null hypothesis 'L(PC/GDP) does not Granger cause L(GDP)' can't be rejected at 5 percent level of significance.

This analysis shows that there is unidirectional causality between log of per capita real GDP [L(GDP)] and log of private sector credit of commercial banks to GDP [L(PC/GDP)]. The test suggests that L(GDP) Granger causes L(PC/GDP) whereas L(PC/GDP) does not Granger causes L(GDP).

In summing up, the result of Granger causality test provides the mixed result. Considering the first Granger causality test, the statistically significant

F-statistic confirms the fact that there is the bidirectional causality between log of per capita real GDP and log of domestic assets of commercial banks to the total domestic assets. Similarly, in the second Granger causality test, the insignificant F-statistic suggests that there is no causality between log of per capita real GDP and log of private sector credit to total credit of commercial banks. Finally, the third Granger causality test shows the unidirectional causality as log of per capita real GDP Granger causes log of private sector credit of commercial banks to GDP but causality in the opposite direction is not supported statistically.

The results of present study partially resembles with the findings of King and Levine (1993a) as they found the strong positive relationship between each of the financial development indicators and the three growth indicators, long-run real per capita growth rates, capital accumulation and productivity growth. Furthermore, the study of Calderon and Liu (2003) revealed that the financial development generally leads economic growth but there is the bi-directional causality between financial development and economic growth. Levine (2004) stressed on co-evolution of finance and growth. Present study also supports these findings as there is the bidirectional causality between log of per capita real GDP and log of domestic assets of commercial banks to the total domestic assets.

Jalil & Ma (2008) found that a positive and significant relationship between financial development and economic growth exists in the case of Pakistan. But, in the case of China, a positive and significant relationship for credit liability ratio and a positive, yet insignificant, relationship with credit to private sector were found. However, in this study there is no causality between log of per capita real GDP & log of private sector credit to total credit of commercial banks. Also, there is the unidirectional causality as log of per capita real GDP Granger causes log of private sector credit of commercial banks to GDP but there is no causality in the opposite direction.

Bhetuwal (2007) and Poudel (2005) found that financial development contributes positively to domestic economic growth. On the other hand, Shrestha (2005) did not find any significant relationship between economic growth and financial development. The present study suggests the co-integration between development of commercial banks and economic growth although there is bidirectional causality between log of per capita real GDP and log of domestic assets of commercial banks to the total domestic assets; and unidirectional causality between log of per capita real GDP and log of private sector credit of commercial banks to GDP. In this context of mixed results, the appropriate development of Nepalese financial sector is essential so that it can play a critical and positive role in the economic growth of the nation.

CONCLUSIONS

This study explored the degree of relationship between the financial revolution, development of commercial bank and economic growth in a developing country - Nepal. Much of the existing literature on the relationship between development of commercial bank and economic growth is presented in a positive light. Alternatively, critical literature presents a market failure view on the relationship (or lack of it) between financial development and economic growth. The analysis has clearly depicted the real picture of evolution of Nepalese commercial banks. Nepalese financial system was not liberalized until 1984, although there were couples of banks and financial institutions. The initiation in financial sector reforms and introduction of liberal economic policies led a rapid expansion of financial institutions and instruments. It has resulted for diversification of financial system during a short span of time. Additionally, the development of new financial instruments and services, introduction of regulatory framework and institutionalization of savings has created new scene for economic growth and development.

The existence of co-integration implies that there is long-run relationship between log of real GDP per capita and log of commercial bank assets to total domestic assets; also between log of per capita GDP and log of total credit available to the private sector through commercial banks to GDP. However, no co-integrating relationship is found between log of real GDP per capita and log of commercial banks' credit to private sector to total credit.

Granger causality test provides the mixed result. The statistically significant F-statistic confirms the fact that there is the bidirectional causality between log of per capita real GDP and log of domestic assets of commercial banks to the total domestic assets. Similarly, the insignificant F-statistic suggests that there is no causality between log of per capita real GDP and log of private sector credit to total credit of commercial banks. Granger causality test also shows the unidirectional causality as log of per capita real GDP Granger causes log of private sector credit of commercial banks to GDP but causality in the opposite direction is not supported statistically.

Economy of the country cannot reach to its growth potential and develop at an adequate pace without an active contribution of the financial sector. A well functioning financial system efficiently mobilizes resources and allocates capital for productive investment projects. Commercial banks are the largest financial institutions dominant in the financial system occupying the major portion of the total financial assets. The development of commercial banks' is important to the speed and direction of economic growth, by mobilizing idle financial resources for productive investment. To link up commercial banks' development and economic growth, the economic activities in the private sector must go simultaneously to strengthen the growth and reducing mass poverty.

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